

Chemical Examination of the *Hibiscus furcatus* Seed Oil

C. S. C. RAO* and S. S. NIGAM

Department of Chemistry, University of Saugar,
Sagar-470 003 (M.P.)

Manuscript received 4 November 1978, accepted 27 April 1979

*HIBISCUS furcatus*¹⁻² (Malvaceae) locally known as Kondagongura in Telugu and Pachapuli in Malayalam is mainly distributed in the hotter parts of India and Ceylon. An infusion of the roots in water is a good cooling drink for the hot weather (Talbot). The present work deals with the chemical examination of the seeds with special reference to the fixed oil which has not been reported so far.

Experimental

Hibiscus furcatus seeds were procured from the local market of Krishna District, Andhra Pradesh, after proper identification. The seeds (2 Kg) were powdered and extracted with petroleum ether (60-80°) in a Soxhlet. Removal of the solvent gave a greenish yellow fixed oil in an yield of 24.2%. The physicochemical constants of the oil were determined: Sp. gr. at 28°: 0.9138; α_D^{20} : 1.4692. Acid value: 2.788; Saponification value: 192.0; Iodine value: 99.3 and Acetyl value: 28.6. The oil (150 gms) was saponified by refluxing with 45 gms of potassium hydroxide in ethanol (95%, 750 ml) for three hours. After distilling off the excess alcohol, the soaps formed were dissolved in water. The unsaponifiable matter was extracted with ether from the aqueous soap solution and mixed fatty acids were liberated by the procedure described by Hilditch³. The oil was found to contain 1.65 gms of reddish yellow unsaponifiable matter (1.1%) and 129 gms of mixed fatty acids (86%). The following constants of the mixed fatty acids were determined: Saponification value: 206.4; Iodine value: 106.2; Neutralisation value: 207.5 and Mean equivalent weight: 280.3.

The mixed fatty acids (100 gm) were separated into saturated and unsaturated acids by Twitchell's method⁴ as modified by Hilditch⁵. The percentage composition of saturated acids (22 gm) and unsaturated acids (78 gm) in the mixture has been determined. 12-13-epoxyoleic acid (8.5%) was isolated from the freshly extracted oil by the method of Hopkins and Chisholm⁶. The identity of the epoxy acid was established by analysis (Found: 72.81; H, 10.59; Calc. for C₁₈H₃₂O₂; C, 72.93, H, 10.88%), conversion to 12-13-dihydroxyoleic acid and by determination of the oxirane oxygen content of the oil by the hydrochloric acid ether method of Swern et al⁷.

The qualitative and quantitative composition of the component acids of the mixed fatty acids were determined by PC, TLC and GLC of the methyl esters (Table 1) using authentic specimens.

TABLE—1

Fatty Acid	Value of Weight %
Palmitic	20.4
Stearic	2.1
Oleic	32.7
Linoleic	36.3

Preparative TLC of the unsaponifiable matter over silicagel-G with ethyl acetate (10%) in benzene has showed presence of four spots. The constituents of the unsaponifiable matter were separated by column chromatography over alumina. The column was eluted successively with different proportions of petroleum ether (60-80°) and chloroform. The first fraction gave a small amount of hydrocarbon mixture. A pale yellow viscous oil was recovered from the second fraction and it responded to Nair and Mager reaction for γ -tocopherol⁸. The peaks of the I.R. spectrum were identical with those of authentic γ -tocopherol. The third fraction contained a pale yellow substance which gave a positive Liebermann-Burchard test and Noller's test. The compound was identified as β -amyirin (m.p. 142°) by Co-TLC with authentic specimen and comparison of the I.R. spectra. The last fraction recrystallised from methanol as feathery white needles, m.p. 136°. The compound gave a positive sterol test; Co-TLC with authentic specimen and I.R. spectrum confirmed the compound to be β -sitosterol.

Hibiscus furcatus seeds yield 24.2% of fixed oil, which has been found to be a glyceride of palmitic (20.4%), stearic (2.1%), 12-13 epoxyoleic (8.5%), oleic (32.7%) and linoleic (36.3) acids. The unsaponifiable matter consists of γ -tocopherol, β -amyirin and β -sitosterol.

The plant grows in all climates and in any type of soil. The high percentage of oil and the presence of γ -tocopherol which acts as a natural antioxidant is suggestive of a possible use of this oil for edible purposes, after examining its toxicity.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (C.S.C. Rao) is grateful to the C.S.I.R. New Delhi, for providing a J.R.F. for carrying out this work.

References

1. The Wealth of India, Vol. V (Raw-materials) 1959, 89; C. S. I. R. Publication, New Delhi.

* Present address: Dr. C. S. C. Rao, Lecturer in Chemistry, A. N. R. College, Gudivada, Krishna (Dist), A. P 511 301.

2. R. N. CHOPRA, S. L. NAYAR and I. C. CHOPRA, *Glossary of India Medicinal Plants* (1956) 133; C. S. I. R. Publication, New Delhi.
3. T. P. HILDITCH, *The Chemical Constitution of Natural Fats*, (1956), 573. Chapman & Hall, London.
4. J. TWITCHELL, *Indian Eng. Chem.*, 1921, 12, 806.
5. T. P. HILDITCH, *The Chemical Constitution of Natural Fats*, (1956) 574. Chapman & Hall, London.
6. C. Y. HOPKINS and M. J. CHISHOLM, *J. Amer. Oil Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 36, 95.
7. D. SWERN, T. W. FINDLEY, G. N. BUKEN and J. T. SCANLAN, *Anal. Chim.*, 1947, 19, 414.
8. F. D. SMELL, C. T. SMELL and C. A. SMELL, *Calorimetric Methods of Analysis*, Vol. III-A (1961), 71, D. Van Nostrand Co., Inc. Princeton, London.

Kinetics of Oxidation of Aromatic Ketones by Alkaline Hexacyanoferrate(III)

A. K. KASHYAP, R. C. MOHAPATRA

and

N. C. KHANDUAL

Department of Chemistry, Khallikote College,
Berhampur-760 001, Ganjam, Orissa*Manuscript received 15 May 1977, accepted 13 April 1978*

POTASSIUM ferricyanide is classified as an oxidising agent in which the oxidising species is a complex electron-abstracting ion¹ and the reactions are thought to proceed by a radical mechanism². The kinetics of oxidation of a number of organic compounds by hexacyanoferrate(III) have been studied by a number of workers³⁻⁶, though similar studies on aromatic ketones are not many. Speakman and waters⁷ have studied the kinetics of oxidation of aldehydes, ketones and nitroparaffins with alkaline ferricyanide. We have reported the oxidation of aromatic ketones by Mn(III)⁸, Ti(III)⁹, Cr(VI)¹⁰ and K₂S₂O₈¹¹. The present investigation deals with the oxidation of acetophenone and some ketones of the naphthalene series.

The ketones, acetophenone, 1-acetylnaphthalene and 2-acetylnaphthalene were used, were of B.D.H. (A.R.) grade and were purified as described earlier¹². The kinetics of these oxidations were studied in 30% (V) methanol-water mixture in alkaline medium at constant ionic strength. The method of rate measurement is similar to our previous method¹³.

The rate of disappearance of hexacyanoferrate(III) follows first order rate law and the reaction is also first order with respect to the organic substrate. The overall bimolecular rate constants for the oxidation of 1-acetylnaphthalene show fairly concordant values at all concentrations of the reductants. Under the condition of constant ionic strength, the oxidations are directly proportional to

the concentration of the alkali and hence the order with respect to the alkali concentration is unity.

The effect of varying ionic strength was also investigated by adding potassium chloride. The rate of the reaction was found to be increased with the increase of the ionic strength of the medium, which is a dominant characteristic of ion-ion reaction. The reaction has been studied in various methanol-water binary mixtures. The decrease in the dielectric constant of the medium results in a decrease in the rate constant. This supports the evidences in favour of the ion-ion reaction.

The reaction was studied in three different temperatures and the activation parameters were evaluated (Table 1).

TABLE I—REACTION RATES AND ARRHENIUS PARAMETERS FOR THE ALKALINE HEXACYANOFERRATE(III) OXIDATION OF AROMATIC KETONES IN METHANOL-WATER MIXTURES

[Hexacyanoferrate(III)]=0.004M, [Ketone]=0.02M
[OH⁻]=0.06M, μ=0.4M, Solvent=30% (V) Methanol-Water

Substrate	k × 10 ⁵ Sec ⁻¹ at °C			E K cal Mole ⁻¹	-ΔS [‡] e.u.
	30	35	40		
1-Acetylnaphthalene	7.67	11.51	19.19	15.36	28.74
2-acetylnaphthalene	3.88	6.71	10.51	20.94	11.94
Acetophenone	2.87	5.75	7.67	22.41	5.17

The kinetic data obtained, agree well with derived rate equation. A plot of 1/k versus 1/S passes through origin indicating the absence of complex formation. The reaction involves the interaction between two negatively charged ions or between a negatively charged ion and a polar molecule and thus should correspond to a negative entropy change. This has been found true in many radical reactions¹⁴⁻¹⁵. For the reactions involving the interaction between similarly charged ions, the plots of log k against the reciprocal of dielectric constant would be a straight line, having negative slope. In the present investigation, similar results have also been obtained which substantiate the experimental results.

The observed rates conform to the following order of reactivity (Table 1) 1-acetylnaphthalene > 2-acetylnaphthalene > acetophenone.

The rate of oxidation of 1- and 2-acetylnaphthalene is faster than acetophenone under similar conditions. The greater reactivity of naphthalene ketone may be due to the enhanced stability of the enolic form of the ketone through which the reaction proceeds to give rise to the product. The greater reactivity of 1-acetylnaphthalene over 2-acetylnaphthalene is due to the well established theory that 1-position of naphthalene can tolerate a developing charge to a greater extent than the 2-position¹⁶.